

1. Conceptual model for settlements

2. Conceptual model for administrative units

3. Physical model

Table: VariableSettlements

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
VariableSettlements	Identifiers	serial
VariableSettlements	Names	text
VariableSettlements	codgik_gid_fk	int4
VariableSettlements	ahp_fk	text
VariableSettlements	ofrm_fk	int4

Table: SettlementLocations

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementLocations	Identifiers	serial
SettlementLocations	VariableSettlementIdentifiers	int4
SettlementLocations	StartsAt	date
SettlementLocations	EndsAt	date
SettlementLocations	the_geom	geometry
SettlementLocations	Source	text
SettlementLocations	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: SettlementManifestations

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementManifestations	Identifiers	serial
SettlementManifestations	Names	text
SettlementManifestations	VariableSettlementIdentifiers	int4
SettlementManifestations	Types	int4
SettlementManifestations	StartsAt	date
SettlementManifestations	EndsAt	date
SettlementManifestations	Geometries	geometry
SettlementManifestations	NameIdentifiers	int4
SettlementManifestations	TypeIdentifiers	int4
SettlementManifestations	LocationIdentifiers	int4
SettlementManifestations	MereologyIdentifiers	int4
SettlementManifestations	Mereology	int4

Table: SettlementMereologyLinks

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementMereologyLinks	LinkIdentifiers	serial
SettlementMereologyLinks	StartsAt	date
SettlementMereologyLinks	EndsAt	date
SettlementMereologyLinks	PartIdentifiers	int4
SettlementMereologyLinks	WholeIdentifiers	int4
SettlementMereologyLinks	Source	text
SettlementMereologyLinks	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: SettlementNames

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementNames	Identifiers	serial
SettlementNames	Names	_text
SettlementNames	VariableSettlementIdentifiers	int4
SettlementNames	StartsAt	date
SettlementNames	EndsAt	date
SettlementNames	Source	text
SettlementNames	AlternativeNames	text
SettlementNames	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: SettlementProvenienceLinks

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementProvenienceLinks	LinkIdentifiers	serial
SettlementProvenienceLinks	ToIdentifiers	int4
SettlementProvenienceLinks	FromIdentifiers	int4
SettlementProvenienceLinks	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: SettlementToAdministrativeUnit

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	Identifiers	serial
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	AdministrativeUnits	int4
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	VariableSettlementIdentifiers	int4
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	StartsAt	date
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	EndsAt	date
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	adm_unit_cname	text
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	adm_unit_ctype	text
SettlementToAdministrativeUnit	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: SettlementTypes

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementTypes	Identifiers	serial
SettlementTypes	VariableSettlementIdentifiers	int4
SettlementTypes	SettlementTypeIdentifiers	int4
SettlementTypes	StartsAt	date
SettlementTypes	EndsAt	date
SettlementTypes	Source	text
SettlementTypes	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: SettlementTypesDictionary

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
SettlementTypesDictionary	Identifiers	serial
SettlementTypesDictionary	Names	text
SettlementTypesDictionary	Categories	text
SettlementTypesDictionary	Defined	bool
SettlementTypesDictionary	References	text
SettlementTypesDictionary	Authors	text
SettlementTypesDictionary	Import	bool
SettlementTypesDictionary	OntoEditorPL	text
SettlementTypesDictionary	Comments	text

Table: VariableAdministrativeUnits

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
VariableAdministrativeUnits	Identifiers	serial
VariableAdministrativeUnits	Names	text
VariableAdministrativeUnits	AdministrativeUnitTypeIdentifiers	int4
VariableAdministrativeUnits	prg_fk	int4
VariableAdministrativeUnits	src_id	text
VariableAdministrativeUnits	type_grp	int4
VariableAdministrativeUnits	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: AdministrativeUnitLocations

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitLocations	Identifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitLocations	VariableAdministrativeUnitIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitLocations	StartsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitLocations	EndsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitLocations	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: AdministrativeUnitLocationsSets

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitLocationsSets	Identifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitLocationsSets	geom_id	int8
AdministrativeUnitLocationsSets	obr_id	int8

Table: AdministrativeUnitAreas

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitAreas	gid	serial
AdministrativeUnitAreas	geom	geometry

Table: AdministrativeUnitManifestations

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	Identifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	Names	text
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	VariableAdministrativeUnitIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	Types	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	StartsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	EndsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	Geometries	geometry
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	NameIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	TypeIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	LocationIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	MereologyIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	Mereology	int4
AdministrativeUnitManifestations	TypesGrp	int4

Table: AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	LinkIdentifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	WholeIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	PartIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	StartsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	HappensWithin	date
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	EndsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitMereologyLinks	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: AdministrativeUnitNames

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitNames	Identifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitNames	Names	_text
AdministrativeUnitNames	VariableAdministrativeUnitIdentifiers	int4
AdministrativeUnitNames	StartsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitNames	EndsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitNames	_type	int4
AdministrativeUnitNames	HistoricalSource	int4

Table: AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Identifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Names	_text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	StartsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	EndsAt	date
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Scope	text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	StartsAtDomination	date
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	EndsAtDomination	date
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	LegalBasis	text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Remarks	text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Bibliography	text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Author	text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	MetadataCreationDate	date
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	in_ontology	int4
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Religion	_text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Confession	_text
AdministrativeUnitSystemsDictionary	Rite	_text

Table: AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	Identifiers	serial
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	Names	_text
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	Types	text
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	Remarks	text
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	LevelsLinkUp	int4
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	system_id	int4
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	Levels	int4
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	TypesId	int4
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	MapLevel	int4
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	MapName	text
AdministrativeUnitTypesNamesDictionary	in_ontology	int4

Table: HistoricalSources

TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	TYPE_NAME
HistoricalSources	Identifiers	serial
HistoricalSources	Names	text